

ELECTRON BEAM AND GAMMA RAY RADIATION TREATMENTS TO ACHIEVE HIGH STRENGTH IN CARBON NANOTUBE LAMINATES

Cecil Evers^{1,2}, Jin Gyu Park^{1,2}, Britannia Vondrasek^{3,4}, Christopher Johnson^{1,2}, Terrencia Martin^{1,2}, Mike Czabaj⁴, Gregory Odegard⁵, and Richard Liang^{1,2*}

¹FAMU-FSU College of Engineering, Florida State University
2025 Pottsdamer St, Tallahassee FL, USA
*Email: liang@eng.famu.fsu.edu

²High Performance Materials Institute, Florida State University
2005 Levy Ave, Tallahassee FL, USA

³Aerospace Engineering Department, United States Naval Academy
Annapolis, MD, USA

⁴Department of Mechanical Engineering, University of Utah
Salt Lake City, UT, USA

⁵Mechanical Engineering – Engineering Mechanics
Michigan Technological University, Houghton, MI, USA

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ABSTRACT

Gamma ray and electron beam irradiation are used to improve the tensile properties of scalable ultra-high volume fraction laminates made from continuous carbon nanotube (CNT) yarns. Radiation treatments simultaneously induce crosslinking and surface activation, enhancing load transfer. Yarns are treated with doses ranging from 50 kGy to 1200 kGy (gamma ray) and 40 Mrad to 300 Mrad (electron beam). Gamma ray treatment yields up to a 5% increase in specific modulus and 4.7% in specific strength, while electron beam treatment achieves increases of up to 10% and 8.9%, respectively. Surface modification is assessed via DCAT which showed a lower contact angle after irradiation, indicating the addition of functional groups. Raman spectroscopy is also used to evaluate surface changes by comparing I_D and I_G peaks. Laminate-scale specimens assess the combined impact on tensile and surface properties. Unidirectional laminates with ~80 wt.% CNTs are fabricated. The 700 kGy gamma ray laminate achieved a specific modulus of 258 GPa g⁻¹ cm³, and the 40 Mrad electron beam laminate achieved a specific strength of 2.29 GPa g⁻¹ cm³. Results demonstrate that radiation treatments enhance load transfer in CNT yarn laminates, with crosslinking playing a critical role in achieving performance beyond state-of-the-art CFRPs.

1 INTRODUCTION

Carbon nanotubes (CNTs) have mechanical and transport properties beyond current state-of-the-art materials, however achieving nanoscale properties at the macro scale remains a challenge. A key limitation of CNT-based laminates is the weak interface between CNT bundles and polymer resin systems [1], [2], [3], [4].

Crosslinking and functionalization by irradiation may mitigate this issue [5], [6], [7], [8], [9]. Other functionalization approaches have limited effectiveness on commercially available CNT yarns due to their dense and aligned networks and large diameters relative to carbon fiber [10]. Additionally, the graphitic nature of CNT yarns has resulted in very low interface strengths, with fracture usually occurring within the CNT yarns themselves [3]. Radiation techniques like gamma ray or electron beam may penetrate the dense CNT networks and provide not only surface functionalization but also

crosslinking in the interior structure [11]. There is a theoretical limit where damage to the CNT structures will become greater than effects from crosslinking and functionalization; thus a range of treatments are necessary [12].

This work compares the effects of electron beam and gamma ray treatments on highly aligned MREALON[®] high strength 2-ply CSY CNT yarns, manufactured by Nanocomp Technologies, Inc. (now part of Huntsman Advanced Materials). Tensile testing of single CNT yarns is used to evaluate the effectiveness of treatment methods on improving tensile properties of the CNT materials. Dynamic contact angle testing (DCAT) is used to evaluate the effectiveness of treatment methods on improving the interface of CNT yarns. Changes to both tensile and interface properties are evaluated by comparing laminate-scale specimens made with treated yarns and CYCOM[®] 5250-4 bismaleimide resin, supplied by Syensqo.

2 METHODS

2.1 Electron Beam Treatment

CNT yarn was wrapped around aluminum mandrel and exposed to a high-energy electron beam with 1.5 MeV. Electron beam dose depends on the exposure time; operation was paused between each 20 Mrad dose to avoid excessive temperature increase in the sample area. CNT yarns were treated with doses of 40, 200, and 300 Mrad. Additional batches of yarns were treated at 40 and 300 Mrad for manufacturing into CNT yarn laminates.

2.2 Gamma Ray Treatment

Gamma ray irradiation was conducted at the Radiation Center, Oregon State University, using the Co60 isotope with 1.13 and 1.33 MeV photon energies. The CNT yarns were wrapped around a plastic tube and placed at the center of the irradiation chamber. The dose was controlled by the irradiation time. Six different doses were applied: 50 kGy, 100 kGy, 200 kGy, 400 kGy, 700 kGy, and 1200 kGy. Composite laminates were made from 200, 700 and 1200 kGy samples.

2.3 Ozone Treatment

Yarns were wound on a truss and placed in a container for even ozone flow. An LG-7 CD Laboratory Ozone Generator was used at 9 V output at 5 L min⁻¹. The treatment was controlled by exposing yarns for 1 hour and 3 hours.

2.4 Yarn Tensile Testing

CNT yarns were tested at large gauge lengths of 120 mm according to a previously published paper [13]. A Shimadzu Autograph AGS-X mechanical test system using Grip-Engineering Thümler GmbH TH76-1+Ko capstan grips with 2.5 cm diameter and a 500 N load cell were used. The loading rate was 3 N min⁻¹, and strain was calculated by crosshead displacement between 0.5 – 1.0%. Crosshead extension was used for the modulus calculations presented in this work due to the small size of the yarns. This makes direct comparison of modulus values with the laminate-scale specimens unsuitable; however, we assume that the trends remained consistent regardless of if an extensometer was used.

2.5 Dynamic Contact Angle Testing

Dynamic contact angle was measured using a Dataphysics DCAT15. The sample was advanced into and receded from deionized water at 1 mm min⁻¹ speed with an immersion depth of 3 mm, which was repeated for 5 cycles. A wetted length was used for DCA calculations based on the measured perimeter of the yarns using a digital microscope.

2.6 Laminate Manufacturing

Unidirectional CNT yarn composite laminates were fabricated using a filament winder and confined mold as shown in Figure 1a-d. Yarns were wrapped in the recessed area of the mold, shown in Figure

1a, then densified (1b), then a thin film of CYCOM[®] 5450-4 BMI is applied to the densified yarn stack (1c) and cured for 6 hours at 204 °C in a hot press [10]. The resultant laminate is shown in Figure 1d.

Figure 1: (a) CNT yarns wound on recessed mold, (b) yarns after densification, (c) resin applied to yarns, and (d) The laminates after curing. (e) shows a cross section image of the laminate.

The laminates manufactured with this technique have extremely high reinforcement concentrations, of over 80 wt.% CNTs. Figure 1e shows an SEM micrograph of the cross section of a laminate embedded in mounting resin. Typical composite cross sections have clear distinctions between the reinforcement and the matrix, but the densification step plastically deforms the CNT yarns together and limits resin content to an extremely low amount between adjacent yarns. This allows for favorable reinforcement-dominated properties when compared with state-of-the-art carbon fiber composites. Moreover, the high degree of densification and mechanical interlock mitigates the low interface strength of CNTs with polymer resins [10].

2.7 Laminate Tensile Testing

The CNT yarn composite laminates were cut to 2-3 mm wide by 80 mm long tensile test coupons and an aluminum jig was used to obtain a consistent gauge length of 25 mm. An Instron 5969 load frame equipped with a 50 kN load cell and MTS 646 hydraulic collet grips were used and tested at 0.3 mm min⁻¹. Strain was calculated with an Epsilon One optical extensometer. The modulus was taken via loading, unloading, and reloading cycles over the range from 400 MPa to 1200 MPa [14].

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Specimens from a single roll of yarns were sent for electron beam and gamma ray treatment to minimize any effects of roll-to-roll variation. The effects of treatment on mechanical properties were measured by tensile testing individual CNT yarns, while functionalization was measured with DCAT and Raman spectroscopy. Both effects were evaluated by fabricating laminate scale specimens with polymer resin to form a comprehensive assessment of the viability of irradiation treatment techniques. Due to the large quantity of yarn required for laminate fabrication, each laminate was made with a different roll of yarn from the same lot.

3.1 Electron Beam Treatment

Measuring the cross-section area of CNT yarns is impractical at scale, so the SI units of linear density were used: tex (g km⁻¹). Linear specific tensile strength, reported in units of (N/tex) is dimensionally equivalent to volumetric specific strength units of (GPa g⁻¹ cm³).

Results from tensile testing of CNT yarns are shown in Figure 2. Tex, shown in Figure 2a, tended to increase with temperature, except for the lowest treated specimen of 40 Mrad which was below the control. Figure 2b compares how the ultimate force varied with treatment, with no clear linear trend ($r = 0.45$). Therefore, the specific properties are dominated by the changes in linear density, resulting in the 40 Mrad yarn demonstrating an increase in both specific strength and specific stiffness while the 200

Mrad dose was most like the control and the higher mass of the 300 Mrad specimens caused it to have the lowest specific properties.

Figure 2. Electron beam treated CNT yarn tensile results. (a) compares linear density in units of tex (g km⁻¹), (b) compares ultimate force, (c) specific strength, and (d) specific modulus.

Raman spectroscopy was used to evaluate the ratio of the I_D band to I_G band. Increases in disorder related I_D band indicate potential functional sites after electron beam treatment. Figure 3a shows a significant increase in the I_D band in a randomly oriented CNT network, while Figure 3b shows the trend holds for the CNT yarns. The I_D band at 300 Mrad treatment is most similar to a gamma ray treatment of 50 kGy, shown in Figure 3b.

Figure 3. Raman spectroscopy comparing I_D and I_G of (a) randomly oriented CNT sheet treated with electron beam, and (b) CNT yarns treated with electron beam or gamma ray.

Figure 2 shows decreasing specific tensile properties with treatment, while Figure 3 suggests increasing interface properties. Therefore, a laminate scale specimen which relies on both is needed to gain a comprehensive assessment of the effectiveness of electron beam treatment. Interestingly, the higher properties at lower dose shown in Figure 2c and 2d are also present in the laminate scale specimens in Figure 4a and 4b. The most significant improvement was in the specific strength at a treatment of 40 Mrad, which reflects the yarn tensile results. However, the improved interface may be responsible for the slight increase in both specific strength and modulus at 300 Mrad, since those properties decreased in the yarn tensile test.

Figure 4. Electron beam treated CNT yarn laminates (a) specific strength and (b) specific modulus.

3.2 Gamma Ray Treatment

Gamma rays cause damage to CNT walls, opening sites for cross linking between adjacent CNT bundles and functional groups on the outer surface. The dose was controlled by altering the time the specimen was exposed to the source, allowing for a large quantity of yarn to be treated.

Figure 5 compares how the tensile properties of the yarns evolved with treatment. As the dosage increased so did the mass of the yarns and therefore also the linear density, shown in Figure 5a. This effect was more pronounced at higher dosage. Figure 5b shows a concurrent increase in ultimate force which increased linearly with treatment ($r = 0.955$), unlike the electron beam. However, the increase in force was less than the increase in tex, so the specific strength, expressed in units of N tex^{-1} , decreased at the higher levels of treatment, shown in Figure 5c. The 200 kGy specimen had the highest specific strength, and while this may be due to the low tex measurement, it also had the highest specific modulus, shown in Figure 5d.

Figure 5. Gamma ray treated CNT yarn (a) linear density, and tensile results. (b) shows ultimate force, (c) specific strength, and (d) specific modulus.

Dynamic contact angle measures both the initial interaction with the liquid, in this case deionized water, and the effect of advancing and receding through the medium. The average contact angle of the yarns which were later used for laminate scale specimens is reported in Figure 6. There is a clear inverse relationship between treatment and contact angle, indicating the presence of functional groups which will likely increase the interface between treated CNT yarns and various polymer resin systems.

Figure 6. Average dynamic contact angle of the CNT yarns used for the gamma ray treated laminates.

There exists an optimal dose which combines the ideal amount of cross linking and surface functionalization, therefore treated CNT yarns were fabricated into laminate scale specimens. These specimens combine the effects on mechanical properties of the yarns in Figure 5 with the interface properties in Figure 6. Each treated laminate had greater specific strength and modulus than the control, shown in Figure 7a and 7b, respectively. The optimal combination for proved to be the 700 kGy treatment, due to combining the effects of increased specific mechanical properties and increased interface properties.

Figure 7. Gamma ray treated laminate tensile (a) specific strength and (b) specific modulus.

3.3 Ozone Treatment

The primary goal of ozone treatment is to functionalize the surface of the CNTs to improve bonding with resin. Like other treatments, the linear density slightly increased with exposure to ozone, shown in Figure 8a. Unlike other treatments, the ultimate force steadily decreased ($r = 0.997$) with treatment because ozone does not crosslink the dense CNT network but damage the CNT structures. Accordingly, Figure 8c shows the treatment resulted in decreased specific strength, while the specific modulus (Figure 8d) was relatively unaffected.

Figure 8. Ozone treated CNT yarn tensile results including (a) linear density, (b) ultimate force, (c) specific strength, and (d) specific modulus.

Figure 9 shows the advancing, receding, and average contact angle of ozone treated yarns and deionized water. While both treatments decreased the contact angle, the difference between one hour and three hour treatment was minimal.

Figure 9. DCAT of yarns exposed to ozone for varying times.

4 CONCLUSIONS

Figure 10 shows how radiation treated CNT composites compare with state-of-the-art unidirectional carbon fiber composites. Laminate properties seem to depend on both crosslinking and surface activation. Gamma ray and electron beam treatments improved both specific strength and modulus over the control laminate; there was an optimal dose of 40 Mrad for the electron beam treatment and 700 kGy for the gamma ray. While ozone treatment may be easier to implement, it was likely not as effective in adding functional groups to improve the interface as the radiation techniques. Additionally, the lack of crosslinking means that ozone treatment by itself will likely have limited success in improving CNT yarn laminate mechanical properties.

Figure 10. Chart comparing specific strength and specific modulus of radiation treated CNT yarn laminates and state-of-the-art unidirectional composites.

The laminate results show that both interface properties and tensile properties must be considered when using single yarn-scale specimens to predict the performance of composite specimens. The optimal dose in both cases was a treatment that improved both mechanical and interface properties, with lower doses not having as much improvements, or higher doses reducing mechanical properties.

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REFERENCES

- [1] A. De Leon, M. Tank, and R. Sweat, “A scalable fiber bundle pullout manufacturing method for data-driven interfacial shear strength measurements of micro and nanomaterials,” *Compos. Sci. Technol.*, vol. 222, p. 109375, May 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.compscitech.2022.109375.
- [2] M. H. Kirmani, G. Sachdeva, R. Pandey, G. M. Odegard, R. Liang, and S. Kumar, “Cure Behavior Changes and Compression of Carbon Nanotubes in Aerospace Grade Bismaleimide-Carbon Nanotube Sheet Nanocomposites,” *ACS Appl. Nano Mater.*, vol. 4, no. 3, pp. 2476–2485, Mar. 2021, doi: 10.1021/acsanm.0c03013.
- [3] J.-W. Kim *et al.*, “Modifying carbon nanotube fibers: A study relating apparent interfacial shear strength and failure mode,” *Carbon*, vol. 173, pp. 857–869, Mar. 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.carbon.2020.11.055.
- [4] J. Bourdeau, K. J. Mintz, B. Jony, M. H. Kirmani, K. Gupta, and S. Kumar, “Improvement of apparent IFSS and specific modulus of CNT yarns,” *Compos. Part B Eng.*, vol. 284, p. 111683, Sep. 2024, doi: 10.1016/j.compositesb.2024.111683.
- [5] M. C. Evora *et al.*, “Single-step process to improve the mechanical properties of carbon nanotube yarn,” *Beilstein J. Nanotechnol.*, vol. 9, pp. 545–554, Feb. 2018, doi: 10.3762/bjnano.9.52.
- [6] S. G. Miller *et al.*, “Increased Tensile Strength of Carbon Nanotube Yarns and Sheets through Chemical Modification and Electron Beam Irradiation,” *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces*, vol. 6, no. 9, pp. 6120–6126, May 2014, doi: 10.1021/am4058277.
- [7] J. Y. Cai *et al.*, “Enhanced mechanical performance of CNT/Polymer composite yarns by γ -irradiation,” *Fibers Polym.*, vol. 15, no. 2, pp. 322–325, Feb. 2014, doi: 10.1007/s12221-014-0322-9.
- [8] M. C. Evora, D. Klosterman, K. Lafdi, L. Li, and J. L. Abot, “Functionalization of carbon nanofibers through electron beam irradiation,” *Carbon*, vol. 48, no. 7, pp. 2037–2046, Jun. 2010, doi: 10.1016/j.carbon.2010.02.012.
- [9] M. H. Kirmani *et al.*, “Using a carbon fiber sizing to tailor the interface-interphase of a carbon nanotube-polymer system,” *Compos. Part B Eng.*, vol. 247, p. 110284, Dec. 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.compositesb.2022.110284.
- [10] C. E. Evers *et al.*, “Scalable High Tensile Modulus Composite Laminates Using Continuous Carbon Nanotube Yarns for Aerospace Applications,” *ACS Appl. Nano Mater.*, p. acsanm.3c01266, Jun. 2023, doi: 10.1021/acsanm.3c01266.
- [11] J. G. Park *et al.*, “Gamma-ray irradiation to achieve high tensile performance of unidirectional CNT yarn laminates,” *Carbon*, vol. 216, p. 118530, Jan. 2024, doi: 10.1016/j.carbon.2023.118530.
- [12] V. Skákalová, “Effect Of Gamma-Irradiation on Single-Wall Carbon Nanotube Paper,” in *AIP Conference Proceedings*, Kirchberg, Tirol (AUSTRIA): AIP, 2003, pp. 143–147. doi: 10.1063/1.1628005.
- [13] Y.-S. Dessureault *et al.*, “Tensile performance and failure modes of continuous carbon nanotube yarns for composite applications,” *Mater. Sci. Eng. A*, vol. 792, p. 139824, Aug. 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.msea.2020.139824.
- [14] B. Vondrasek, C. Evers, C. Jolowsky, G. M. Odegard, Zhiyong Liang, and M. Czabaj, “Characterization of multidirectional carbon-nanotube-yarn/bismaleimide laminates under tensile loading,” *Compos. Part B Eng.*, vol. 280, p. 111465, Jul. 2024, doi: 10.1016/j.compositesb.2024.111465.